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Review Article

Therapeutic Potential of *Vitex Negundo L.* in Managing Inflammatory Induced Disorders

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ABSTRACT

Vitex negundo L. (Family: Verbenaceae), commonly known as Nirgundi, is a resilient medicinal herb traditionally valued for its wide-ranging therapeutic applications. Every part of the plant including its leaves, bark, roots, seeds, fruits, and flowers has been utilized in indigenous systems of medicine for treating numerous health conditions. Phytochemical research has revealed the presence of various active constituents such as volatile oils, flavonoids, triterpenes, diterpenes, sesquiterpenes, lignans, glycosides, iridoid glycosides, and stilbene derivatives, which contribute to the plant's pharmacological versatility. In recent times, there has been a renewed interest in herbal treatments for neurological and mental health disorders. With a significant portion of India's population affected by mental illnesses and limited access to effective treatments, *Vitex negundo* offers promising potential as an alternative remedy. Ancient Ayurvedic literature supports its efficacy in this domain. The Charaka Samhita describes it as useful in eliminating parasites (Krimighna), neutralizing toxins (Vishaghna), and managing Vata disorders often linked with nervous system imbalances. In Sushruta Samhita it is placed in the Surasadi Gana, it pacifying Kapha (Shleshma Shamana), while the Ashtanga Hridaya related these properties. Additionally, the Bhavaprakasha Nighantu refers to it as Smritida, indicating its role in enhancing memory. This review compiles both classical and modern findings to present *V. negundo* as a potent herbal drug for neurological and cognitive disorders. The convergence of traditional knowledge and modern research underscores its potential for future development as a plant-based therapeutic agent for brain and nerve-related conditions.

INTRODUCTION

ननष्कास्य व्याधीन गुण्डयतीनत शरीरं रक्षतीनत ,
गुडी रक्षणे।

Nirgundi known as *Vitex negundo* Linn., family (Verbenaceae) or the five-leaved chaste tree in (english), is a tall, aromatic shrub-. This plant is easily recognized by its quadrangular stems and

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leaves that are divided into three to five leaflets. It produces bluish-purple flowers grouped in hairy, branched clusters. It typically grows in moist areas such as riverbanks, wastelands, and open forests and is native to regions including India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Thailand, Malaysia, Eastern Africa, and Madagascar.^[1] It is also cultivated in many parts of the world, including Asia, Europe, North America, and the West Indies for its medicinal and agricultural value. It grows up to 3 meters in height and is commonly found at the altitudes of 1500 meters.^[2] *Vitex negundo* has long been valued in traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, and Chinese medicine, where it is praised for its ability to manage a wide range of health issues. It is referred to as ‘*Sarvaroganivarani*’, meaning a universal remedy. An old Indian saying claims that diseases won’t prevail where *Nirgundi* are found—if their uses are known.^[3] Every part of the plant holds medicinal significance, traditionally used to treat inflammation, fungal infections, liver disorders, and oxidative stress-related issues. In modern times, herbal medicine has regained popularity globally as a safer and more natural alternative to synthetic drugs.^[4] *V. negundo* continues to be a subject of growing interest in scientific research, which increasingly validates its traditional uses. Studies have confirmed its therapeutic potential, particularly in supporting liver health, and its role in preventing and managing various diseases. The increasing global demand for plant-based treatments has highlighted the need for scientific validation, and *Vitex negundo* stands out as a promising candidate for the development of new plant-derived pharmaceuticals, thanks to its rich phytochemistry and proven medicinal value.^[5]

Methodology

This review article is based on a thorough analysis of research on *V. negundo*. Comprehensive

literature searches were performed using keywords such as “*V. negundo*,” “*Nirgundi*,” “*vitexin*,” “*anti-inflammatory*,” “*Nirgundoside*,” and related terms across major scientific databases, including PubMed, Web of Science, PMC, Google Scholar, Springer, ScienceDirect, and ResearchGate. The review focused on studies addressing the phytochemistry, pharmacokinetics of major active phytomolecules, pharmacological activity, anti-inflammatory effects, and health benefits of *V. negundo*. Articles were selected from last 10 years. Studies not related to biosynthesis methods and metabolic reactions were excluded, and only English-language publications were considered.

Taxonomic Classification of *Vitex negundo*^[6]

Taxonomic Rank	Classification
Kingdom	Plantae
Sub Kingdom	Tracheobionta
Super Division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Sub Class	Asteridea
Order	Lamiales
Family	Verbenaceae
Genus	<i>Vitex</i>
Species	<i>Vitex negundo</i>

Vernacular Names of *Vitex negundo*^[7]

Language	Name(s)
English	Five leaved chaste tree
Tamil	Nirkundi, Vellai-nochi
Telugu	Vaavili
Hindi	Shivari, Nirgundi
Malayalam	Vellanocchi, Indranee, Karunacci
Kannada	Nkkilu, Lakkigida, Nekka, Nakkigida
Punjab	Shwari
Assam	Aslok
Bengal	Nirgundi, Nishinda
Gujarati	Nagod
Marathi	Nirgundi
Punjabi	Sambhalu, Banna
Sanskrit	Nirgundi

Morphology

Vitex negundo is a tall-growing medicinal shrub or occasionally a small-sized tree, usually reaching a height between 2 to 8 meters (approximately 6.5 to 26 feet). The outer stem covering has a reddish-brown tone and appears coarse and dry. The leaves are compound and radiate from a central point, generally made up of five narrow, spear-like leaflets, though three-parted leaves are also sometimes seen.^[8] Each leaflet measures about 4 to 10 cm long, with the central leaflet being the largest and joined to the main stalk by a short connecting stem. The leaf borders are finely saw-edged, and the lower surface is covered in tiny, soft hairs.^[9] A large number of flowers bloom in loose, branched bunches known as panicles, which extend 10 to 20 cm in length. Individual flowers are around 6 to 7 cm long and come in shades of pale blue, lavender, or white. The petals are different size, at the bottom center petal being the most elongated. The outer floral parts (calyx and corolla) are densely covered with short hair-like outgrowths. It produces a soft, rounded fruit that turns dark purple to black when mature and contains four small seeds, each about 4 mm wide.^[10]

Geographical Distribution of *V. negundo*.

Vitex negundo flourishes in damp and humid environments, typically seen growing along streams, open scrublands, and partially wooded landscapes. Its natural range spans multiple countries, such as India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Malaysia, Madagascar, and parts of Eastern Africa. Beyond its wild growth, the plant is also intentionally cultivated in different parts of the world, including Asia, Europe, North America, and the West Indies, primarily due to its agricultural and commercial value.^[11] In addition to its recognized therapeutic benefits, *Vitex negundo* is also utilized for timber production and

occasionally as a food source. Within India, it is commonly found throughout the country, especially in lower Himalayan foothills and various regions of Himachal Pradesh, where it grows at altitudes reaching up to 1500 meters.^[12]

Nirgundi in the Samhita Period.

- In the *Charaka Samhita*, *Nirgundi* is categorized under the groups *Krimighna* (anti-parasitic) and *Vishaghna* (anti-toxic). It is used in the treatment of *Vata*-disorders.^[13]
- In the *Sushruta Samhita*, it is included in both the *Surasadi* group and the *Shleshma Shamana* (Kapha-pacifying) category.^[14]
- The *Ashtanga Hridaya* also places *Nirgundi* under the classifications of *Vishaghna*, *Surasadi*, and *Shleshma Shamana*.^[15]
- Throughout the *Samhita* literature, the terms *Nirgundi* and *Sinduvara* are frequently used. Traditional Ayurvedic scholars interpret white-flowered varieties as *Sinduvara*, while the blue-flowered types are referred to as *Nirgundi*.^[16]

Nirgundi in the Nighantu Period.

- In the traditional Ayurvedic text *B.p Nighantu*, *Acharya* refers to *Nirgundi* as *Smritida*, highlighting its ability to enhance memory. Similarly, *Acharya Kaiyadeva* classifies it as *Medhya*, signifying its beneficial effects on intelligence and cognitive function.^[17]
- Detailed information on its *Rasapanchaka* (five-fold properties), therapeutic actions (*karma*), and varieties (*bheda*) can be found in texts such as the *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Shodala Nighantu*, and *Nighantu Ratnakara*.^[18]

- Most Ayurvedic (*Nighantukaras*) agree that *Nirgundi* possesses properties that help balance *Vata* and *Kapha doshas*, and consider it effective in managing parasitic infections (*Krimighna*) and skin disorders.^[19]

Table 4: Ayurvedic Properties of *Vitex negundo* Linn.^[20]

Property	Description
<i>Rasa</i> (Taste)	<i>Katu</i> (Pungent), <i>Tikta</i> (Bitter)
<i>Guna</i> (Quality)	<i>Laghu</i> (Light), <i>Ruksha</i> (Dry)
<i>Virya</i> (Potency)	<i>Ushna</i> (Hot)
<i>Vipaka</i> (Post-digestive effect)	<i>Katu</i> (Pungent)
<i>Doshakarma</i> (Dosha Action)	<i>Kapha-Vata Shamaka</i> (Alleviates Kapha and Vata)

Ethnobotanical Significance of *Vitex negundo*

Vitex negundo is widely recognized across various regions for its medicinal value in folk and traditional healing systems. In the Chittagong area of Bangladesh, it is commonly used to manage health issues such as fatigue, headaches, nausea, malaria, and kala-azar (black fever).^[21] In Guangdong, China, where it is locally known as Buing'iab, the plant is traditionally administered for treating cold-related symptoms like coughs, flu, and the common cold.^[22]

Moving to Nepal, particularly the Kali Gandaki region, the herb known as Simali is used for respiratory conditions, including sinus infections and whooping cough.^[23] In Pakistan, its traditional applications are diverse across different localities. For example, in Buner, it is referred to as Marvandaey and employed to relieve chest pain and backache, and also as a natural toothbrush.^[24] In Kot Manzaray, it is valued for its anti-allergic properties. In the Siran Valley, locals call it Kalgari and use it in veterinary practices, especially to treat digestive discomfort in buffaloes. In the Margallah Hills, it is used under the name Nirgud to help manage skin and gum disorders.^[25]

In the Philippines, although its local name is not recorded, the plant is traditionally believed to aid in cancer treatment. In Sri Lanka, it is known as Nilnikka and is widely used to address eye conditions, dental pain, and rheumatism. Additionally, it is considered beneficial as a general tonic, digestive aid, and anti-parasitic remedy.^[26]

Microscopy of *Vitex negundo*

The petiole consists of a single-layered epidermis with numerous unicellular, bicellular, and multicellular (uniseriate) non-glandular hairs, along with glandular trichomes that have a stalk of one to three cells and a head of one or two cells. The cortex includes an outer collenchyma layer and an inner zone of 6–8 layers of parenchyma.^[27] The basal region has well-developed collenchyma, which reduces towards the upper regions. Pericyclic fibres are absent at the base but appear as an incomplete ring in the upper part, encasing a central, horseshoe-shaped vascular bundle. Additionally, a few small vascular bundles are found ventrally between the arms of the main bundle, with two or occasionally three bundles situated externally.^[28]

Lamina Structure: The leaf blade has a single epidermal layer mainly with unicellular hairs, while bi- and multicellular and glandular hairs are occasionally observed. The hypodermis is typically 1–3 layers thick, with interruptions that expose 4–8 layers of palisade cells rich in chlorophyll. Numerous vascular veins traverse the mesophyll, each surrounded by a bundle sheath. Stomata are located only on the lower (ventral) side and are densely covered by trichomes. The leaf shows 23–25 vein-islets and 5–7 vein terminations.^[29]

Leaf Powder: Powder microscopy reveals several structures such as whole and fragmented trichomes

(unicellular, bicellular, and multicellular types), glandular hairs, palisade cells beneath the hypodermis, both epidermal layers, and pitted xylem vessels.^[30]

Phytochemical Constituents screening of *V. negundo*.

V. negundo is known to contain a wide range of bioactive compounds discovered through various phytochemical analyses. The plant is rich in flavonoids, lignans, terpenoids, and volatile oils. In addition to these, it also contains flavones, glycosides, indole glycosides, triterpenes, diterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and stilbene derivatives.^[31]

Among the key compounds isolated from the leaves are glucosidic iridoids such as negundoside and nishindaside, along with viridiflorol, beta-caryophyllene, sabinene, 4-terpineol, gamma-terpinene, and various phenolic constituents. The methanolic extracts of the plant have shown the presence of antibacterial flavonoids and related compounds. Additionally, root extracts of *V. negundo* have yielded compounds such as Negundon A and Negundo B, which are known for their tyrosinase-inhibiting properties.^[32]

Compounds Isolated from Different Parts of *V. negundo*

Flavonoids^[33]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
1	5-Hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone	Leaf
2	5,7-Dihydroxy-6,4'-dimethoxyflavone	Leaf
3	Luteolin	Leaf
4	Luteolin-7-O- β -D-glucoside	Leaf
5	7,8-Dimethylherbacetin-3-rhamnoside	Leaf
6	Vitegnoside	Leaf
7	Iso-orientin	Leaf
8	Chrysoplenetin	Seed
9	Chrysosplenol D	Seed
10	4',5-Dihydroxy-3,6,7-trimethoxyflavone	Seed
11	5,3'-Hydroxy-6,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone	Leaf
12	5,7,3'-Trihydroxy-6,8,4'-trimethoxyflavone	Leaf
13	Acerosin-5-O-glucoside	Leaf
14	Corymbosin	Leaf, Twig
15	5-Hydroxy-6,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone	Leaf, Twig
16	5,6,7,8,3',4',5'-Heptamethoxyflavone	Leaf
17	Casticin	Seed
18	5,3'-Hydroxy-7,8,4'-trimethoxyflavone	Stem bark
19	3,6,7,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone-5-O-glucopyransylrhamnoside	Stem bark
20	5-Hydroxy-6,7,8,4'-tetramethoxyflavone	Leaf, Twig
21	Vitexin cafeate	Stem bark
22	5-Hydroxy-3,6,7,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone	Leaf, Seed
23	Vitexicarpin	Leaf
24	Vitexin cafeate	Stem bark
25	3,6,7,3',4'-Pentamethoxy-5-O-glucopyranosylrhamnoside	Stem bark
26	4'-O-methylmyricetin-3-O-[4''-O- β -D-galactosyl]- β -D-galactopyranoside	Stem bark
27	3,4,5,7,3',4',5'-Hexahydroxy-6,8-dimethoxyflavone	Leaf, Twig
28	4,5-Dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone-6-O-rhamnoglucoside	Leaf, Twig
29	5,7-Dihydroxychromone	Seed

Lignans^[34]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
30	Coniferyl aldehyde	Seed
31	Trans-3,5-dimethoxy-4-hydroxycinnamic aldehyde	Seed
32	2-Methoxy-4-(3-methoxy-1-propenyl)-phenol	Seed
33	Secoisolariciresinol diglucoside	Seed
34	Matairesinol	Seed
35	Vitrofolal E	Root, Seed

Terpenoids^[35]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
66	Negunfurol	Seed
67	4,6-Dimethyl-11-formyl-1-oxo-4H,2,3-dihydronaphthofuran	Seed, Root, Stem bark
68	4,6-Dimethyl-11-dimethoxymethyl-1-oxo-4H,2,3-dihydronaphthofuran	Stem bark
69	1,6-Dioxo-2(3),9(10)-dehydrofuranoeremophilane	Seed
70	Negundion F	Seed
71	Negundoal	Seed
72	Vitedoin B	Seed
73	Negundoin A	Seed
74	Negundoin B	Seed
75	Negundoin C	Seed
76	Negundoin G	Seed
77	3 β -Hydroxy-abieta-8,11,13-trien-one	Seed
78	Negundoin E	Seed
79	Negundol	Seed
80	6-Acetoxy-9,13-epoxy-16-methoxy-labdan-15,16-olide	Seed
81	Negundion D	Seed
82	Betulinic acid	Leaf
83	Negundonorin A	Seed
84	Ursolic acid	Leaf
85	Negundonorin B	Seed
86	3-epi-Corosolic acid	Stem bark
87	3 β -Acetoxyolean-12-en-27-oic acid	Leaf
88	2 α ,3 α -Dihydroxyoleana-5,12-dien-28-oic acid	Leaf
89	2 β ,3 α -Diacetoxyoleana-5,12-dien-28-oic acid	Leaf
90	2 α ,3 β -Diacetoxy-18-hydroxyoleana-5,12-dien-28-oic acid	Leaf
91	β -Amyrin	Leaf callus culture
92	3-Acetyloxy-11-en-28-oic acid prophyll ester	Leaf callus culture
93	3-Acetyloxy-11-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid butyl ester	Leaf callus culture
94	Oleanolic acid	Leaf callus culture
95	2 α ,3 α ,23-Trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid methyl ester	Leaf callus culture
96	2 α ,3 α -Dihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid	Leaf callus culture
97	2 α ,3 α ,23-Trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid	Leaf callus culture

Iridoids^[36,40]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
98	Agnuside	Leaf
99	Negundoside	Leaf

100	1,2-Disubstituted idopyranose	Leaf
101	Glucosylated cyclopentapyran carboxylic acid derivative	Leaf
102	Nishindaside	Leaf
103	6'-p-Hydroxybenzoyl-mussaenosidic acid	Leaf

Steroids^[41,45]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
104	β -Sitosterone	Leaf
105	β -Sitosterone acetate	Leaf
106	Stigmasterone	Leaf
107	24 ζ -Methyl-5 α -lanosta-25-one	Seed
108	β -Sitosterol	Leaf
109	Lanostan-8,25-dien-3 β -ol	Seed
110	7-Oxositosterol	Seed
111	Stigmast-4-en-6 β -ol-3-one	Seed
112	Ergosterol peroxide	Seed
113	22,23-Dihydro- α -spinasterol- β -D-glucoside	Leaf

Other Compounds^[46]

No.	Compound Name	Plant Part
114	Iso-fraxidin	Seed
115	Xanthotoxin	Seed
116	5,8-Dimethoxypsoralen	Seed
118	p-Hydroxy benzoic acid	Leaf
119	n-Hentriacontanol	Leaf
120	Salicylic acid	Leaf

Nirgundoside

Nirgundoside is a secondary metabolite isolated from the leaves of *Vitex negundo* Linn. Traditionally used in folk medicine, this compound is recognized for its anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant properties. Chemically, nirgundoside is classified as an iridoid O-glycoside and is also referred to as 2'-p-hydroxybenzoylmussaenosidic acid.^[47]

Agnuside

Iridoids is a cyclopentane ring structure. These are secondary metabolites derived from monoterpenes and are known for their wide range of therapeutic effects. In various species of the *Vitex* genus, several iridoids-including agnuside, negundoside,

nishindaside, and aucubin—have been identified, often working synergistically with other phytochemicals. These iridoids are considered key contributors to the plant's medicinal properties. Among them, agnuside holds particular importance due to its pharmacological relevance. It also serves as a reliable chemotaxonomic marker, making it useful in the standardization and quality control of *Vitex* plant extracts to ensure consistency and efficacy.^[48]

Luteolin (3', 4', 5, 7-tetrahydroxyflavone)

Luteolin is a naturally occurring flavonoid present in the leaves of the *Vitex negundo* (Nirgundi) plant. Due to its beneficial health properties, luteolin is in high demand and is often included in nutraceutical formulations. It exhibits strong

antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Research indicates that luteolin plays a role in several therapeutic actions, including antimicrobial, anticancer, and antiulcer activities. Additionally, it is used in managing fever, treating wounds and diarrhea, and also functions as a natural insect repellent and pesticide.^[49]

Stigmasterol

Stigmasterol, also referred to as Stigmasterin or Wulzen anti-stiffness factor, is an unsaturated phytosterol commonly found in a variety of medicinal plants. It serves as a key raw material in the synthesis of numerous chemical compounds, both synthetic and semi-synthetic, which are widely used in the pharmaceutical industry.^[50] Scientific research has explored its wide-ranging health-promoting properties, including its effectiveness in reducing inflammation, combating oxidative stress, lowering cholesterol levels, managing diabetes, and protecting against cancer. Additionally, stigmasterol has shown potential in supporting joint health, exhibiting anti-osteoarthritic effects, and providing benefits to the central nervous system.^[51]

Vitexin

Vitexin is classified as flavonoid present in the leaf extract of *V.negundo* and can also be produced through synthesis. This compound has demonstrated potent anticancer activity in preclinical studies involving breast, prostate, liver, and cervical cancers. It can be reliably extracted and quantified from the leaves of *V. negundo*, showing minimal percentage relative standard deviations (% RSDs), which confirms its suitability as a standard marker compound for the plant's leaf extract.^[52]

Vitexicarpin

The bioassay-guided fractionation of the chloroform-soluble extract obtained from the leaves of *Vitex negundo* led to the identification of a flavone compound known as vitexicarpin. This compound displayed significant cytotoxic activity against a range of human cancer cell lines. To further boost the cytotoxic potential of vitexicarpin, multiple acylation processes were performed, producing several derivatives, including a methylated variant (3,5,6,7,3',4'-hexamethoxyflavone), an acetylated form (5,3'-diacetoxy-3,6,7,4'-tetramethoxyflavone), along with six other acylated analogs.^[53]

Vitexicarpin, present in the leaves of *Vitex negundo*, is known for its wide array of medicinal applications. It possesses antibacterial, antitumor, astringent, and anti-acne properties. Additionally, it is used for alleviating eczema, reducing fever, promoting sedation, treating liver disorders, eliminating intestinal worms, repelling parasites and insects, and reducing inflammation. Furthermore, it is helpful in managing catarrhal fever, relieving cough, healing ulcers, treating skin conditions, and stimulating hair growth.^[54]

Pharmacological Significance:

Recognizing its historical use in folk and traditional medicine, researchers have designed and conducted scientific investigations aimed at validating these ethnomedicinal claims through pharmacological evaluation. Leaf decoctions of *Vitex negundo* Linn. have traditionally been employed in the management of various ailments such as inflammation, eye disorders, toothaches, leucoderma, splenic enlargement, ulcers, cancerous conditions, catarrhal fevers, rheumatoid arthritis, gonorrhoea, sinus infections, scrofulous sores, bronchitis, and also as general tonics. Additionally, the plant exhibits diverse therapeutic properties including antibacterial, antipyretic, antihistaminic, ovicidal, growth inhibitory, and

morphogenetic activities. Scientific studies have further confirmed its antigenotoxic, antihistamine, central nervous system depressant, and antifertility effects, particularly associated with its leaves.^[55,56]

Pharmacological Activity on the Nervous System

Anti-Amnesic Activity

The memory-enhancing potential of *Vitex negundo* Linn extract has been demonstrated in experimental models of scopolamine-induced amnesia in rats. The extract was evaluated for its effect on different phases of memory, such as acquisition, consolidation, and retention. It was observed that the extract significantly reduced memory impairment, likely due to its antioxidant properties, which contributed to improved memory function when compared to a standard anti-amnesic agent.^[57]

Further studies using a hydroalcoholic extract of leaves of *Vitex negundo* showed enhancement of learning and memory in mice. These effects were evident in both normal animals and those with scopolamine-induced cognitive deficits, as assessed through behavioral tests like the elevated plus maze and object recognition test. The cognitive benefits observed were suggested to be due to the extract's antioxidant action, possible inhibition of acetylcholinesterase, and enhanced cholinergic neurotransmission.^[58]

In cellular studies, vitegnoside, an active constituent of *Vitex negundo*, provided neuroprotection in a human neuroblastoma cell model mimicking Alzheimer's disease. The compound improved cell viability, maintained membrane integrity, and preserved nuclear structure under amyloid beta-induced toxicity conditions. These effects were linked to its ability to reduce neuronal damage, inhibit mitochondrial-

mediated cell death, and suppress inflammation, likely through modulation of specific signaling pathways involved in neurodegeneration.^[59]

Anxiolytic Activity

The calming (anxiolytic) properties of the ethanolic root extract of *Vitex negundo* Linn were investigated through behavioral studies involving the elevated plus maze (EPM) and the light-dark box test. In this study, male mice were orally administered either *Vitex negundo* root extract or diazepam (used as a standard reference drug) one hour prior to testing. After dosing of *Vitex negundo* extract in animal demonstrated a noticeable increase in both the amount of time spent in the open arms and the number of entries into them on the EPM. Additionally, mice treated with either diazepam or *Vitex negundo* extract spent significantly more time in the light compartment of the light-dark box, indicating a reduction in anxiety-like behavior. These findings suggest that the root extract of *Vitex negundo* exhibits substantial anxiolytic efficacy.^[60]

Anticonvulsant Activity

The essential oils extracted from the fruits, leaves, and flowers of *Vitex negundo* Linn have been evaluated for their potential to prevent seizures. These oils were tested in experimental models that induce seizures in animals, using established methods to assess their effects. In one model, seizures were triggered electrically (maximal electroshock seizures or MES), and in another, chemically induced seizures were produced using pentylenetetrazole (PTZ).⁽⁶¹⁾ Compared to standard anticonvulsant medications such as phenytoin and diazepam, the oil from *Vitex negundo* fruits significantly reduced the duration of seizures and protected against PTZ-induced clonic convulsions. The oil derived from the leaves showed strong protective effects only in the PTZ

model, suggesting selective anticonvulsant activity. Additionally, when given in lower doses (100 mg/kg orally), all tested oils enhanced the effectiveness of both standard drugs. These findings imply that essential oils from *Vitex negundo* may be beneficial as supplementary treatments to reduce seizure frequency and might help lower the dosage requirements of conventional anti-seizure drugs.^[61]

Moreover, further studies were conducted to explore the effects of *Vitex negundo* extract on nerve cell activity. A methanolic extract of the plant was applied to cultured mouse nerve cells under controlled conditions. When exposed to the extract, the cells exhibited reduced sodium ion flow across their membranes, as measured by specialized electrophysiological techniques. The extract inhibited sodium currents in a manner that depended on the dose, and it altered the electrical properties of the cells by shifting the sodium channel activity toward a less excitable state. Importantly, the extract did not affect potassium currents, indicating selectivity in its action. Additionally, the extract significantly decreased the frequency of repetitive electrical firing in brain cells derived from young mice. These findings suggest that the plant extract may help reduce nerve excitability, contributing to its potential to manage seizures and possibly reduce nerve-related pain.^[62]

Anti-Nociceptive Activity

The pain-relieving potential of *Vitex negundo* Linn leaf extract was evaluated using animal models designed to assess both central and peripheral analgesic effects. In one experiment, an ethanolic extract from the leaves was tested using the tail flick method in rats to measure central pain relief, while the acetic acid-induced writhing test in mice assessed peripheral analgesia. Meperidine served as the reference drug in the tail flick test,

and aspirin was used as a standard in the writhing test. Comparisons with these standards showed that the *Vitex negundo* leaf extract exhibited significant anti-nociceptive effects in both models. Additionally, the involvement of central pain pathways was confirmed by observing the interaction of the extract with naloxone hydrochloride, an opioid receptor antagonist, suggesting that the extract has both central and peripheral modes of action in reducing pain.^[63]

Further investigations explored the pain-relieving effects of a fat-soluble (lipophilic) fraction extracted from the seeds of *Vitex negundo*. Specifically, the petroleum ether fraction (PEF) obtained from an aqueous ethanol seed extract was tested in mice across various pain models. At doses of 12, 24, and 48 mg/kg, PEF produced a clear and dose-dependent reduction in pain responses. Significant analgesic effects were observed in chemical-induced pain models such as acetic acid writhing and the formalin test, as well as in models involving thermal stimuli. These findings highlighted the strong anti-nociceptive properties of the petroleum ether seed extract, demonstrating its effectiveness against different types of pain, including those caused by chemical irritation and heat.^[64]

CNS Depressant Activity

A methanolic extract derived from the leaves of *Vitex negundo* has been shown to enhance the sedative effects in mice. Specifically, the extract significantly prolonged the duration of sleep induced by drugs such as pentobarbitone sodium, diazepam, and chlorpromazine, in dose dependent manner indicating its central nervous system depressant properties.^[65]

Analgesic Activity

An aqueous extract prepared from fresh leaves of *Vitex negundo* was tested for its analgesic properties in female Wistar rats using standard methods such as the hot plate test, tail flick test, and formalin-induced pain model. Aspirin (100 mg/kg) was employed as the reference drug in both the hot plate and tail flick tests.^[66]

In a separate study, the analgesic properties of an ethanolic extract from *Vitex negundo* flowers were investigated to determine its effects on both peripheral and central pain mechanisms. Peripheral analgesia was measured using the acetic acid-induced writhing test, while central analgesia was evaluated with the tail flick test, using aspirin as the standard control in both. The findings revealed that the flower extract produced significant pain relief comparable to aspirin in the writhing test and exhibited even stronger analgesic effects than aspirin in the tail flick test, suggesting potent central analgesic activity.^[67]

Neuroprotective Activity

An aqueous leaf extract of *Vitex negundo* has shown promising potential in enhancing cognitive function in Wistar albino rats. When administered orally at a dose of 1000 mg/kg body weight over a period of 15 days, the extract improved learning and memory, as measured by the classical T-maze behavioral test. Biochemical analysis revealed that the extract helped reduce lipid peroxidation, increased the activity of natural antioxidant enzymes, and lowered acetylcholinesterase levels in the brain, suggesting a protective effect against oxidative damage and cognitive decline.^[68]

In another study, the influence of *Vitex negundo* on the growth of neuronal extensions (neurites) was examined in hippocampal neurons isolated from newborn mice. In various concentrations of *Vitex negundo* extract (ranging from 20 to 200 µg/ml) neurons were cultured for 48 hours in a

controlled environment. Neurite formation was identified using a specific antibody marker (βIII-tubulin), and detailed measurements were performed using specialized imaging software. The results indicated that lower concentrations of the extract (30 and 40 µg/ml) significantly promoted the elongation of the longest neurites, whereas higher concentrations (150 and 200 µg/ml) reduced the length of the longest neurites. However, the total neurite length across all concentrations remained unchanged. Overall, these findings suggest that the methanolic extract of *Vitex negundo* may support neuronal growth at specific doses and holds promise as a neuroprotective agent for future therapeutic applications.^[69]

Antioxidant Activity

The protective properties of *Vitex negundo* leaves against oxidative stress in the brain were evaluated in a rat model exposed to ethanol-induced neurotoxicity. Various fractions of a hydromethanolic extract from the leaves were tested for their ability to counteract oxidative damage in brain tissue. Rats were given 20% ethanol (5 ml per 100 g body weight) daily for 28 days to induce oxidative stress in the brain. Examination of brain tissue from ethanol-treated rats revealed significant signs of damage, including gliosis (a response to injury in the brain). However, rats treated with *Vitex negundo* extract fractions showed notable protection against this damage. Histological analysis confirmed that the extract helped preserve brain tissue structure and reduced the harmful effects of ethanol exposure. These findings suggest that *Vitex negundo* leaves offer neuroprotective benefits, likely due to their strong antioxidant properties.^[70]

Biological Activity of *Vitex negundo*

Many plants produce chemical compounds that serve as defense mechanisms, protecting them from pathogens and predators. Research on the antimicrobial properties of *Vitex negundo* extracts indicates that this plant functions effectively as a biocontrol agent. Various studies have demonstrated that these extracts possess the ability to inhibit, suppress, and even eliminate numerous harmful biological agents responsible for diseases and damage. The biological effects exhibited by *Vitex negundo* include.^[71]

Anti -fungal activity

The crude ethanol extract derived from the fruits (seeds) of *Vitex negundo* Linn demonstrated strong antifungal activity, inhibiting *Fusarium solani* by 90%, which is comparable to the standard reference drug. Moderate effectiveness was observed against *Microsporum canis* with a 60% inhibition rate. However, the extract showed negligible antifungal effects on *Candida glabrata* and *Aspergillus flavus* strains. To date, there are no prior studies reporting the antifungal properties of *Vitex negundo* Linn fruits. Understanding the extent and mechanisms by which specific compounds in the plant extracts inhibit pathogens could be valuable for developing natural treatments against fungal and bacterial infections.^[72]

Anti-bacterial activity

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Part used :

Various parts of the Nirgundi plant, including the roots, leaves, flowers, fruits, and bark, are traditionally used for their medicinal value. Each part contributes distinct therapeutic properties, making the plant highly significant in herbal medicine. These components are often employed in the preparation of remedies for a wide range of health conditions due to their diverse biological activities.^[74]

Formulation:^[75]

- Mahavishagarbha taila
- Mahalakshminarayana taila
- Rasnaputeek taila
- Nirgundiyadi upnaha
- Swachchhand bhairav rasa
- Vata vidhwansana rasa

Toxicology study:

Vitex negundo is a widely utilized medicinal plant in the pharmaceutical industry, especially in the development of commercial formulations. Its acute and sub-chronic toxicity profiles have been evaluated following the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) guidelines 402 and 411.^[76] In acute dermal toxicity studies, VN oil was applied at a dose of 2000 mg/kg body weight to both male and female

Wistar rats.^[77] For the sub-chronic assessment, rats received dermal applications of VN oil at doses of 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg body weight, five times a week for a duration of 90 days.^[78]

Throughout the study period, no abnormalities were observed in the animals with respect to behavior, hematological or biochemical parameters, necropsy, or histopathology. According to the Globally Harmonized System (GHS), VN oil falls under Category 5, indicating an LD₅₀ value exceeding 2000 mg/kg. However, individuals with hormone-sensitive conditions such as endometriosis, uterine fibroids, or hormone-related cancers are advised against using Vitex. It is also not recommended during pregnancy. Recent findings suggest that the bioactive chromone compounds found in Vitex possess notable anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties.^[79,80]

Recommended Dosage

Various parts of the plant, including the leaves, roots, bark, fruits, flowers, and seeds, are traditionally used for therapeutic purposes. These can be administered in several forms such as powder, decoction, juice, oil, tincture, paste (with sugar, water, or honey), or as a dry extract. For adults, the suggested dosages are: juice – 10 to 20 ml; decoction – 50 to 100 ml; leaf powder – 1.5 to 3 grams; and dry leaf extract – 300 to 600 mg.^[81]

CONCLUSION

Vitex negundo, widely known as *Nirgundi*, is a versatile medicinal herb recognized for its therapeutic applications in both traditional healing systems and modern medicine. Extensive experimental studies have confirmed its diverse pharmacological effects, including anticancer, antimicrobial, antifeedant, anti-inflammatory,

antihyperpigmentation, hepatoprotective, antihistaminic, and analgesic activities.

Classical Ayurvedic scriptures such as the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* describe *Nirgundi* as a valuable remedy for a variety of health issues. These ancient texts particularly emphasize its effectiveness in addressing inflammation, pain, respiratory ailments, and skin disorders. Various parts of the plant—leaves, roots, bark, seeds, flowers, and fruits—are incorporated into numerous formulations, showcasing its broad-spectrum medicinal utility.

Although traditional and preclinical evidence strongly support the efficacy of *V. negundo*, there remains a critical need for well-designed clinical trials to validate these findings in human subjects. Its longstanding use in traditional medicine, combined with promising scientific data, makes this plant a strong candidate for development into standardized herbal pharmaceuticals. To fully integrate it into contemporary therapeutic frameworks, rigorous research focusing on its active constituents and clinical effectiveness is essential.

To summarize, *Vitex negundo* holds significant therapeutic value, as affirmed by classical Ayurvedic literature and modern research. Advancing its development as a scientifically validated herbal medicine will require continued pharmacological investigations and clinical studies to establish its safety, efficacy, and potential role in evidence-based healthcare.

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